

Research article

The word for ‘mirror’ in French Analysis of *miroir* and *glace* in literary works, 1650–1799

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Abstract: Romance languages such as Portuguese, Galician, Spanish, and Italian inherited words descended from Latin SPECULUM ‘mirror’. However, in the Gallo-Romance languages, Occitan, and Catalan, words derived from the Latin deponent verb MIRARI are used: *miroir* in French, *miralh* in Occitan, and *mirall* in Catalan. In French, *glace*, descendant of Latin GLACIA, is also utilized. The words *miroir* ‘mirror’ and *glace* ‘ice’ appeared in literature from the 12th century. The meanings of *glace* were extended to include ‘mirror’ in 1825, although it is possible that *glace* was so used earlier. In this paper, we analyze the occurrences of *miroir* and *glace* meaning ‘mirror’ in literary works in the period 1650–1799. We clarify that *glace* was used to mean ‘mirror’ before 1825. We also point out that the usage frequency of *glace* meaning ‘mirror’ gradually increased between 1650 and 1799. Furthermore, in the first half of the 18th century, the use of *glace* to indicate the glass part of a mirror began to decline, while that of *glace* to mean ‘mirror’ started increasing. It was around this time that the metonymy of *glace* for *miroir* began in earnest.*

Keywords: miroir (mirror); glace (glass); diachronic linguistics; dialectology; geolinguistics

1. Introduction

Given that Narcissus was looking at his reflection in a body of water in Greek mythology, surfaces of water were probably the first mirrors. Following that, stones and metals whose surface had been polished were used as mirrors. In the 14th century, the technique of processing glass to reflect images was developed.

First, the present article will give an overview of the words for ‘mirror’ in the Romance languages. Second, we will focus on the situation in French. French has two words for ‘mirror’: *miroir* and *glace*. These two words have different etymons.

ITO, Reiko, Takamasa, SEIMIYA, and Yuji, KAWAGUCHI. 2022. The word for ‘mirror’ in French: Analysis of *miroir* and *glace* in literary works, 1650–1799. *Studies in Geolinguistics* 2: 53–65. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7121541>

* This research was supported by Research Center for Science Systems (RCSS) in Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS).

2. Overview of the situations in the Romance languages

2.1. ‘Mirror’ in the Romance languages

Based on the term for ‘mirror’, the Romance languages can be divided into three differentiated areas (see the linguistic landscape presented in Figure 1). Portuguese *espelho*, Galician *espello*, Spanish *espejo*, and Italian *specchio* all come from the Latin etymon SPECULUM ‘mirror’. On the contrary, French *miroir*, Occitan *miralh*, and Catalan *mirall* are nouns derived from the Latin deponent verb MIRARI ‘to watch’. The isolated Romanian form *ogîndă* probably comes from the Old Church Slavic *se oglindati* ‘to look around’ (cf. *DLR* under *ogîndă*).

Traditionally, geolinguistic theory teaches us that the distribution of the term ‘mirror’ in the Romance languages seems to bear witness to the distribution often referred to as “center versus periphery.” According to this theory, the reflexes of Latin SPECULUM, i.e., those in Portuguese, Spanish, Galician, and Italian, show the older layer, while those descending from the Latin MIRARI in French, Occitan, and Catalan are innovations that occurred in an ancient area of SPECULUM. However, this geolinguistic interpretation misses evidence of the pre-existence of forms derived from SPECULUM in French, Occitan, and Catalan during more or less ancient times. The form *espelh* in old Provençal would only be a loan from Italian, and the Piedmont dialect actually knows the loan *spetš* from the Italian *specchio* (cf. *FEW* XII, p. 162). In our current state of knowledge, we do not know if the innovation of MIRARI really occurred in an old field dominated by SPECULUM.

In summary, the greatest question regarding the name for ‘mirror’ in the Romance languages is the absence of forms derived from the etymon SPECULUM in the Gallo-Romance domain and that of Catalan. Let us now review the names for ‘mirror’ in *Atlas Linguistique Roman (ALiR)*.¹

¹ In the following lines, we will not analyze in detail all the variants found in *ALiR*.

Fig. 1 'Mirror' in the Romance languages

The forms [ʃp'aʎu] in Portuguese, [esp'eʎo] in Portuguese and Galician, and [esp'exo] in Castilian all presuppose as the etymon the Latin SPECULUM, although the fate of the consonantal sequence -CL- is not identical: On the western outskirts of the Iberian Peninsula, it is a palatal consonant /ʎ/, and at the center of the peninsula, -CL- changed to a fricative consonant /x/. The borrowing [isp'iʎua] in Basque teaches us that the mirror was not an autochthonous object in the Basque-speaking region but rather a cultural object introduced from the Romance languages.

Despite the voicing of -C- to [g] and the vowel change to [a], we can say that the Rhaeto-Romance form [ʃp'iagal]² still retains the skeleton of SPECULUM. Various forms such as one finds in and around Italy are all derived from SPECULUM: [spj'etʃ] in northern Italy, [sp'ekkjo] in Central Italy, [spicc'ali] in Southern Italy, [sp'idʒu] in Sicily and Sardinia, and [sp'eccu] in Corsica. A single exception would be the form [sp'era] in Central Italy, which comes from the etymon SPĒRA 'ball'.

The situation of Romanian is quite different. First, it can be confirmed that almost everywhere in the Romanian-speaking region, 'mirror' did not belong to the linguistic layer of Romance languages but rather to that of other languages. The most extended form [ogl'ində] in Dacoromanian is borrowed from Old Slavic. Aromanian and Megleno-Romanian, respectively, present the borrowings [yil'ie] from Greek *ύαλί*³ (Segura Da Cruz & Augusto 1993: 118) and [vid'elə] from Bulgarian *vidjalo*. Only one

² It is strictly a phonetic form of Romansh, one of the Rhaeto-Romance languages. The influence of Swiss German on the realization of this form cannot be ruled out.

³ In modern Greek, it is spelled γυαλί 'glass'.

presumably autochthonous form [kətətʷ'are] is attested in the Maramureş region of Transylvania. This form probably comes from the Romanian *căuta-oare* ‘to capture the image’. In the following sections, we will tackle the difficult question of the word for ‘mirror’ in the Gallo-Romance and Catalan areas.

2.2. ‘Mirror’ in French

Figure 2 shows the situation of *miroir* ‘mirror’ in the Gallo-Romance, Occitan, and Catalan dialectal areas in the early 20th century. As mentioned above, descendants of Latin MIRARI, including *miroir* and *miralh*, spread in the southern area of ALF, where descendants of Latin GLACIA ‘ice’ such as *glace* are also present. As Edmont’s interviews did not cover the northern part of ALF, the situation of the Gallo-Romance area is unclear.

There are two possible reasons for this data loss. The first possibility is that even though Gilliéron had included ‘mirror’ in the questionnaire, Edmont forgot to ask about it. The second possibility is that Gilliéron excluded it, but Edmont added it during his inquiry. Gilliéron (1902: 4) describes the word choice of ALF as follows: isolated words, chosen from the popular repertoire, grouped together by similarity of meaning, and more particularly, designated to establish the phonetic laws of the languages.⁴ Edmont started the inquiry in Pas-de-Calais, the area where he was born, situated in the north of France, in 1897. Figure 2 depicts the presence of dialectal forms in this area. However, in *Matériaux de l’Atlas linguistique de la France: N°s 276–286*, one of his original notebooks, the forms for *miroir* are not registered, even though they are listed in the map. This fact suggests that Edmont had not elicited the forms for *miroir* in the first survey, but after having finished the survey, he returned to Pas-de-Calais and surveyed some additional words, including *miroir*. Thus, the first possibility is more realistic.

⁴ “... mots isolés, choisis dans le répertoire populaire, groupés par similitude de sens, et plus particulièrement désignés pour établir les lois phonétiques des parlers.”

○ < Lat. MIRARI ● < Lat. GLACIA □ = both ○ & ●

Fig. 2 ALF1648: *miroir*

According to Rey et al. (1992: 891 & 1251), the word *miroir* was first attested in the 12th century, and it acquired the meaning of “which offers the image of the ideal representation of things and people”⁵ in the 13th century, and to the present day it carries the meaning ‘mirror’. The word *glace* also first appeared in the 12th century. In about 1165, it already had the meanings ‘indifference’ and ‘non-tinned glass plate’. As time passed, the meaning of this word was extended to include ‘mirror’ in 1825. Mirrors are made by silvering or applying a film of silver to plate glass. This indicates that *glace*

⁵ “ce qui offre l’image des choses et des gens, représentation idéale de”

and *miroir* are inseparably linked, which explains why *glace* means ‘mirror’ in modern French.

Table 1 Meanings of *miroir* and *glace* in Rey et al. (1992: 891 & 1251)

century	<i>miroir</i>	<i>glace</i>
12 th	mirror	ice, indifference, non-tinned glass plate
13 th	+ ideal representation	
15 th		+ ice block
17 th		+ icing, window (of coach), ice cream
19 th		+ window, mirror, congealed food

3. Objective

Rey et al. (1992) indicated the first use of *glace* as ‘mirror’ in 1825, but such a use might have occurred much earlier. To clarify this, we analyzed the changes in the number of occurrences of *glace* as ‘mirror’ and *miroir* in literary works before 1800.

4. Methodology

4.1. Corpus

The French written corpus *Frantext 22.2 – Classique* was used as the corpus for this study. *Frantext Classique* includes works from 1650 to 1799, with a total of 1,106 works and 44,746,239 tokens. The words analyzed are *glace*⁶ and *miroir*⁷ in this corpus.

4.2. Method

For this study, we gathered all occurrences of *miroir* and *glace* that appear in the corpus.

We classified *glace* into four types by meaning:

- ice (and derived meanings: cold-hearted, indifference, ice cream)
- plate glass (and derived meaning: window of coach)
- mirror
- unidentifiable

⁶ Including the following spelling variations and plural forms: *glaces*, *glasse*, *glasses*, and *glacies*.

⁷ Including the following spelling variations and plural forms: *miroirs*, *mireur*, and *mireurs*.

A questionnaire was then administered regarding the classifications of *glace*. Four participants (three doctoral students in French studies and one former doctoral student, including Seimiya and Ito) identified the meaning of *glace* on a scale of 0 to 3 (0: *unidentifiable*, 1: *ice*, 2: *plate glass*, 3: *mirror*) for 20 examples of *glace*. Cronbach’s alpha for the questionnaire was $\alpha = .87$. We therefore deemed the questionnaire appropriate.

Examples (1) to (3) show the co-occurrence of *glace* and *miroir*. In these sentences, *glace* indicates ‘glass’, not ‘mirror’. For example, ‘*glace de miroir*’ in (3) is not ‘mirror of mirror’ but rather ‘glass of mirror’. In other words, the meaning of *glaces* here is ‘the material comprising the mirror’ or ‘a part of the mirror’.

(1)	dans	vn	brilliant	miroir
	PREP	INDEF.ART.M	shiny-ADJ.M	mirror-NOM.M
	dont	la	glace	fidelle
	REL.PRON	DEF.ART.F	glass-NOM.F	faithful-ADJ.F

‘in a shiny mirror whose faithful glass’

(ASSOUCY Charles COYPEAU d’ 1653, “Poësies et lettres ... contenant diverses pièces héroïques, satiriques et burlesques,” p. 41, Frantext Q975)

(2)	du	grand	miroir	son
	of. DEF.ART.M	big-ADJ.M	mirror-NOM.M	POSS.ADJ.M
	poing	brise		la
	fist-NOM.M	break-IND.PRES.3SG		DEF.ART.F

glace

glass-NOM.F

‘of the big mirror his fist breaks the glass’

(DEMARETS DE SAINT-SORLIN Jean 1657, “Clovis ou la France chrestienne,” p. 124, Frantext Q748)

(3)	il	ressemble	à
	SUBJ.PERS.PRON.3SG	look like-IND.PRES.3SG	PREP

une	glace	de	miroir
INDEF.ART.F	glass-NOM.F	PREP	mirror-NOM.M

‘it looks like a glass of mirror’

(DU HALDE Jean-Baptiste 1735, “Description géographique, historique, chronologique, politique et physique de l’Empire de la Chine et de la Tartarie chinoise : t. 2,” p. 176, Frantext Q494)

Example (4) shows that *cette glace* refers to the front part of *un miroir*. In this case, *glace* means ‘mirror’ as a kind of metonymy.

(4) on	nomme	cela	
INDEF.PRON.3SG	call-IND.PRES.3SG	DEM.PRON.N	
un	...	<i>miroir</i>	ce
INDEF.ART.M		mirror-NOM.M	DEM.PRON.N
que	tu	vois	
REL.PRON	SUBJ.PERS.PRON.2SG	see- IND.PRES.2SG	
n’	est	que	
ADV.NEG	be-IND.PRES.3SG	CONJ	
ton	image	que	cette
POSS.ADJ.M	image-NOM.M	REL.PRON	ADJ.DEM.F
<i>glace</i>	réfléchit		
mirror-NOM.F	reflect-IND.PRES.3SG		

‘it is called a mirror ... what you see is only your image that this mirror reflects’
(DELISLE DE LA DREVETIÈRE Louis-François 1737, “Arlequin sauvage, Théâtre du XVIIIe siècle 1,” p. 485, Frantext S274)

In (5), *glace* appears without *miroir*. The use of the verb *se mirer* clearly indicates that *glace* here means ‘mirror’.

(5) je	la
SUBJ.PERS.PRON.1SG	PERS.PRON.F

vois		qui	se mire
see-IND.PRES.1SG		REL.PRON	watch oneself-REFL.3SG
dans	une	<i>glace</i>	
PREP	INDEF.ART.F	mirror-NOM.F	

‘I see her who watches herself in a mirror’
 (DEMARETS DE SAINT-SORLIN Jean 1657, “Clovis ou la France chrestienne,” p. 124, Frantext Q748)

Table 2 shows the number of occurrences of *miroir* and *glace* (‘plate glass’ and ‘mirror’) in the period 1650 to 1799, which we subdivided into 25-year periods for each of which we counted the following:

- total tokens
- number of occurrences of *miroir*
- number of occurrences of *glace* meaning ‘plate glass’
- number of occurrences of *glace* meaning ‘mirror’

Table 2 Numbers of occurrences of *miroir* and *glace* (plate glass, mirror)

periods	1650–1674	1675–1699	1700–1724	1725–1749	1750–1774	1775–1799	
total tokens	5796905	6859184	3372085	8494229	10164970	10058866	
<i>miroir</i>	171	186	63	156	153	157	
<i>glace</i>	plate glass	7	18	6	11	10	24
	mirror	7	10	9	43	65	84

5. Analysis

5.1. *Miroir* and *glace* as ‘mirror’ by itself

Table 3 shows the relative frequencies (per 1 million words) of *miroir* and *glace* meaning ‘mirror’. Decimal places are rounded off.

Table 3 Relative frequencies (per one million words) for *miroir* and *glace* as mirror in each period

	1650–1674	1675–1699	1700–1724	1725–1749	1750–1774	1775–1799
<i>miroir</i>	29	27	19	18	15	16
<i>glace</i> as mirror	1	1	3	5	6	8

Figure 3 shows proportions of the relative frequencies (per 1 million words) for *miroir* and *glace* meaning ‘mirror’ for the period 1650 to 1799. The proportion of *glace*

meaning ‘mirror’ gradually increased from 3% in 1650–1674 to 33% in 1775–1799. On the other hand, that of *miroir* declined. Evidently, the use of *glace* for ‘mirror’ expanded during this 150-year period.

Fig. 3 Proportion of the relative frequencies (per 1 million words) for *miroir* and *glace* meaning ‘mirror’

5.2. *Glace* as part of a mirror and *glace* meaning ‘mirror’

We also compared the relative frequencies (per 1 million words) of *glace* as part of a mirror (i.e., *glace du miroir*, *miroir dont la glace*, etc.) and *glace* meaning ‘mirror’. Decimal places are rounded off (see Figure 4.)

The relative frequencies (per 1 million words) of both uses of *glace* were the same from 1650 to 1699. The incidence of *glace* as part of a mirror was maintained at the same level until 1724. Thereafter, such usage was very rare. On the other hand, the relative frequency of *glace* meaning ‘mirror’ has increased since 1700. In other words, *glace* could have two aspects - ‘part of a mirror’ and ‘mirror’ - until the end of the 17th century, but since then, *glace* on its own has increasingly meant ‘mirror’.

Examples such as *glace du miroir* imply that *glace* in reference to the constituent material might have been distinguished from *miroir*, a product with the function of reflecting images. Alternatively, *miroir*, referring to the entire object, could have been distinguished from a reference to the glass part, *glace*, of an object that reflects images. It would appear that the distinction between function (*miroir*) and material (*glace*) or the whole object (*miroir*) versus the glass part (*glace*) fell out of use, which made possible the metonymy of *glace* for *miroir*. It is unclear why this happened in the early

18th century. It could relate to the total amount of glass mirrors produced and their prevalence.

Fig. 4 Relative frequencies (per 1 million words) for *glace* as part of a mirror and *glace* meaning ‘mirror’

6. Discussion and conclusion

The purpose of this study was to determine whether *glace* was used in the sense of ‘mirror’ before 1825.

We have confirmed that the word *glace* was already being used to mean ‘mirror’ during the period 1650–1799 (see Table 3 and Figure 3). *Miroir* was always the predominant word for ‘mirror’, while usage of *glace* to mean ‘mirror’ gradually increased during the examined period.

Furthermore, until the early 18th century, *glace* was used to describe both ‘part of a mirror’ and ‘mirror’. Thereafter, the use of *glace* solely to indicate ‘mirror’ became widespread. This use constitutes a kind of metonymy wherein *glace* refers to *miroir*.

Abbreviations

<i>ALF</i>	<i>Atlas linguistique de la France</i>
<i>ALiR</i>	<i>Atlas Linguistique Roman</i>
<i>ATILF</i>	<i>Analyse et Traitement Informatique de la Langue Française</i>
<i>DLR</i>	<i>Dicționarul limbii române</i>

FEW *Französisches etymologisches Wörterbuch. Eine Darstellung des galloromanischen Sprachschatzes*

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URL

ATILF (1998-2022) *Frantext*. Nancy. URL: <https://www.frantext.fr/> (accessed 2022-07-25).

Publication history

Date accepted: 19 August 2022